
Temperature dependence of the photochromism of naphthopyrans in functionalized sol–gel thin films

Rosario Pardo, Marcos Zayat and David Levy*

Instituto de Ciencia de Materiales de Madrid, CSIC, 28049 Cantoblanco, Madrid, Spain.

E-mail: d.levy@icmm.csic.es; Fax: 34 913 720 623

A photochromic naphthopyran derivative, 3-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3*H*-naphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran, was embedded in sol–gel prepared phenyl (Ph) and pentafluorophenyl (pFPh) functionalized silica thin films. The functionalization of the matrix surface and the temperature both play important roles in the photochromic properties of the dye molecules as they affect their interaction with the embedding ormosil matrix and, therefore, the equilibrium between coloured and colourless forms of the molecule. The bleaching kinetics of the dye embedded in these ormosil matrices were strongly accelerated by temperature in all samples, particularly in pFPh functionalized matrices, due to the reduced mobility of the molecules at low temperatures. The usage of different amounts of organic functional substituents in the matrix has an important effect on the size of the pores where the photochromic molecules are located affecting the steric hindrance of the mechanism of formation of the coloured forms. The ability to control the dye–matrix interactions allows the design of materials with defined photochromic properties.

Introduction

The photochromism of naphthopyrans (NP) has been widely studied in the last decade due to the high photostability of these molecules upon irradiation with UV light.^{1–7} Analogously to the spiropyrans, the photochromic mechanism of these molecules involves a photoinduced cleavage of the C(sp³)–O bond of the pyran ring leading to an equilibrium between the colourless form and a set of stereoisomers of the coloured form with different stabilities, constituting a system with a distinct absorption in the visible range spectrum. The system reverts thermally to its original colourless form, as shown in Fig. 1.

The chemistry of the photochromic naphthopyrans has been thoroughly explored by Merlini in the early 1970s.⁸ The most interesting photochromic properties of NP, such as the absorption spectra upon irradiation with UV light and the kinetics of the bleaching (*i.e.* recovery of the original whiteness), have been studied in different solvents or in organic polymer matrices.^{2–7} The introduction of NP molecules into inorganic matrices was successfully accomplished using the sol–gel method.⁹ This method, being a low temperature process, allows the preparation of hybrid organic–inorganic ormosil matrices¹⁰ and the doping of these matrices with optically active organic molecules.^{11–13} In previous works, we have demonstrated the feasibility of introducing photochromic naphthopyran derivatives into sol–gel ormosil matrices,⁹ and the effect of different organic functional substituents in the matrix on the photochromic properties of the embedded molecules.^{14,15} In a similar way as solvatochromic compounds

in liquids,¹⁶ the polarity of the environment where the molecules are located has a strong influence on their photochromic properties.^{17,18} Moreover, the size and shape of the pores containing the dye molecules also have an important effect on the spectral and kinetic properties of the photochromic system, as they may provoke steric inhibition during the mechanism of formation of the coloured forms.^{9,12,19}

This work will focus on the interactions between the photochromic molecules and the embedding matrix, and the effect of the temperature on the bleaching kinetics processes in the different pore environments. Two different organic functional substituents, Ph (phenyl) and pFPh (pentafluorophenyl), with similar size but different polarities, were chosen to prepare the organically functionalized matrices. The nature of the matrix, as well as the temperature, will have an important effect on the equilibrium between the coloured and colourless forms of the photochromic molecules and the relative amounts of the different forms of the coloured merocyanines.

Experimental

Materials

Tetraacetoxysilane (TAS) and pentafluorophenyltriethoxysilane (pFPhTES) were from ABCR. Phenyltriethoxysilane (PhTES) and tetrahydrofuran (THF) were purchased from Aldrich Chemicals. Ethanol was from Merck. For all preparations double-distilled water was used. The photochromic molecule used for the preparation of samples, 3-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3*H*-naphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran, was generously donated by PPG Industries, Inc. The chemical structures of the closed and open forms of the photochromic molecule⁷ are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Chemical structure of the 3-(2,4-dimethoxyphenyl)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3*H*-naphtho[2,1-*b*]pyran molecule and a set of stereoisomers of the coloured form.

Preparation of films

Samples were prepared from mixtures of TAS and the corresponding organically modified alkoxide RTES (R = Ph (phenyl) and pFPh (pentafluorophenyl)) in the appropriate ratio to obtain ormosil matrices. The maximum R/Si molar ratios used for sample preparation were 0.9 and 0.7 for Ph and pFPh functionalized samples respectively, as larger amounts of organic functional substituents in the matrices resulted in the formation of opaque films. Water was added to allow the hydrolysis of the alkoxide precursors. The ratio of water to hydrolyzing groups was kept at 1 : 1 for all samples. The reaction was self-catalyzed by the slow release of acetic acid from the TAS during hydrolysis. The mixtures were allowed to hydrolyze for 24 hours under stirring at 25 °C. The photochromic molecules were added as a THF solution after the hydrolysis of the sol, to give a photochromic dye : Si molar ratio of 1 : 200. THF was used as solvent due to the possibility of obtaining highly concentrated solutions and good miscibility with the coating sol. The deposition of the films was carried out after the addition of the photochromic dye using the spin-coating technique with the sample holder spinning at 2000 rpm. A 0.1 mL portion of the sol was used for the preparation of each film. The films were further dried for 24 hours at 100 °C. The samples were named after the organic functional substituents used for preparation followed by the atomic percentage of the modified Si atoms in the matrix. Table 1 summarizes the compositions of the sols used for film preparation. The amount of the dye in the sols was kept constant for all samples (0.01 molar).

Characterization

The photochromic samples were irradiated with a 365 nm, 100 W, B-100AP UV lamp from UVP. The thickness of the films was measured using a Taylor-Hobson Form Talysurf-50 profile analyzer. The morphology was measured using an

Table 1 Chemical compositions of the sols used for film deposition. R represents Ph or pFPh

Sample name	Molar composition			
	TAS	RTES	H ₂ O	R/Si
R90	0.20	1.80	6.20	0.90
R70	0.60	1.40	6.60	0.70
R50	1.00	1.00	7.00	0.50
R30	1.40	0.60	7.40	0.30
R10	1.80	0.20	7.80	0.10
R0	2.00	0.00	8.00	0.00

atomic force microscope (Nanoscope IIIa, from Veeco) in tapping mode with silicon cantilevers. The absorption spectra of the resulting films as well as the kinetics of the bleaching process were measured, at a constant temperature between 10 and 60 °C, using a Varian Cary 50 Bio UV-Visible spectrophotometer. The absorption spectra were measured between 300 and 800 nm and are given as $DAbs$ ($A_{a.i.} - A_{b.i.}$), where $A_{a.i.}$ and $A_{b.i.}$ are the absorptions after and before irradiation, respectively. The bleaching kinetics were monitored vs. time at the wavelength of the maximum absorption of each sample (visible range). The kinetic constants k_1 and k_2 were calculated from the bleaching curves using a bi-exponential decay equation:

$$A(t) = A_0 + A_1 e^{-k_1 t} + A_2 e^{-k_2 t}$$

Results and discussion

The photochromic properties of the naphthopyran (NP) molecules embedded in phenyl (Ph) and pentafluorophenyl (pFPh) functionalized silica matrices were characterized as a function of temperature. These matrices were chosen in order to induce a change in the polarity of their inner pore surface,

Fig. 2 Scheme of a pore in Ph (left) and pFPh functionalized matrices (right) where the photochromic molecules are located.

Fig. 3 AFM 3D images showing the surface of the Ph and pFPh modified ormosil matrices (R/Si = 0.5) and the measured RMS roughness values.

where the molecules are located. One of the most important differences observed between samples prepared with Ph or pFPh substituents is that much thicker films are obtained in matrices prepared with Ph substituents than those prepared with the same amount of pFPh substituents. This is due to the higher polarity of the pentafluorophenyl substituents, which allows the formation of hydrogen bonds with the Si–OH groups of the surface of the pores, reducing the overall volume of the pores (Fig. 2). This observation is also supported by AFM micrographs of the surface of the films, Fig. 3, showing a much greater surface roughness in the Ph modified ormosil matrices as compared with the analogous pFPh functionalized films.

In both Ph and pFPh functionalized matrices, the thickness of the films (given in Fig. 4) increases progressively with the relative amounts of Ph or pFPh substituents (Table 1) used for the preparation of the matrix, the effect being more pronounced in Ph functionalized samples.

On the other hand, the interactions between the naphthopyran molecules and the Ph or pFPh functionalized matrices have an important effect on the photochromic properties of these materials. The most important of these properties are: the absorption spectra upon irradiation with UV light, particularly the intensity and position of the absorption band, and the kinetics of the bleaching (*i.e.* recovery of the original whiteness).

Colour intensity of the absorption band

The maximum intensity of the absorption band of the samples during irradiation decreases considerably as the temperature is

increased in both pFPh and Ph functionalized samples, the latter showing a much steeper change (Fig. 5). This effect is due to the transitions existing between the coloured and colourless forms of the molecule (Fig. 1), which favour the colourless form (closed form) of the dye by temperature. The intensity of the absorption band of the films before and after irradiation is given in Fig. 6 as a function of the temperature.

The intensity of the absorption band of the films in the dark (before irradiation) increases slightly as the temperature is increased. This effect, only observed in pFPh functionalized

Fig. 4 Thickness of the resulting film as a function of the amount of Ph and pFPh substituents in the ormosil matrix.

Fig. 5 UV-Vis absorption spectra of the naphthopyran molecules in the ormosil matrix at different temperatures: a) Ph70, b) pFPh70.

Fig. 6 Intensity of the absorption band in films before and after irradiation with UV light as a function of the measuring temperature.

samples (Fig. 6), is related to the smaller pore volume of these samples (Fig. 2) that results in steric hindrance to the formation of the coloured forms, which is diminished with the increasing mobility of the dye at higher temperatures. In Ph functionalized samples, this effect is not observed due to the low polarity of the matrix, which can not stabilize the coloured merocyanine when the sample is not irradiated.

The amount of organic functional substituents in the matrices is also a factor affecting the intensity of the absorption band of the photochromic films during irradiation. Fig. 7 shows the intensity of the band in Ph and pFPh functionalized samples as a function of the amount of organic functional substituents in the matrix and the temperature. The values are given after being normalized with the thickness of the films (e), according to Beer-Lambert's law. In both, Ph and pFPh functionalized matrices, the intensity of the absorption at any given temperature decreases as the amount of Ph or pFPh substituents in the matrix is increased, the effect being more pronounced in pFPh functionalized matrices. Moreover, in pFPh functionalized samples an important

Fig. 7 Normalized intensity of the absorption band of the samples during irradiation as a function of the amount of Ph (left) or pFPh substituents (right) at different temperatures.

Fig. 8 Absorption spectra of the irradiated NP molecules in Ph and pFPh functionalized matrices, measured at 20 μ C.

increase in the intensity of the band is observed for samples having a pFPh/Si ratio of 0.7 (sample pFPh70). This can be explained by the decrease in polarity of the pore surface as the percentage of Ph or pFPh substituents in the matrix is increased, resulting from the screening of the highly polar OH groups on the surface of the pore by the larger organic functional substituents.¹⁴ In highly functionalized pFPh matrices the pore volume is reduced to an extent to force the photochromic molecules to occupy voids with a larger relative amount of OH groups, which are able to stabilize the coloured form of the dye, increasing therefore the intensity of the band.

Spectral position of the absorption band of the coloured form

The absorption band of the NP molecules in Ph functionalized matrices (Fig. 8) has a maximum (λ_{max}) between 488 nm in sample Ph90 and 507 nm in sample Ph10. This maximum was also found to depend on the temperature. In pFPh functionalized matrices a significant red shift is observed as compared to the analogous Ph functionalized samples. This shift, attributed to the higher polarity of the pFPh substituents,¹⁴ is in agreement with the different polarities of benzene and pentafluorobenzene, as measured by Reichardt,¹⁶ who assigned polarities of 34.3 and 38.4 on the $E_T(30)$ scale respectively. Table 2 summarizes the positions of the absorption bands of Ph and pFPh functionalized samples.

The absorption band of the coloured form of the photochromic naphthopyran in Ph and pFPh functionalized matrices shows a very slight shift to the UV as the temperature is increased between 10 and 60 μ C, which is much more pronounced in pFPh functionalized samples (see Table 2). One possible explanation for this observation is that the low mobility of the photochromic molecules in the pFPh functionalized matrices (smaller pores) limits the formation of the *trans*-isomer (Fig. 1), which is only generated by the rotation of the *cis*-isomer.²⁰ In addition, the λ_{max} of the absorption band of the *trans*-isomer shows a slight UV shift with respect to that of the *cis*-isomer.²¹ The mobility of the dye in the

Table 2 Absorption maxima (nm) of the naphthopyran dye in Ph and pFPh functionalized ormosil matrices after irradiation with UV light at different temperatures

Matrix	Group	%	$\lambda_{max}/\mu\text{C}$					
			10 μ C	20 μ C	30 μ C	40 μ C	50 μ C	60 μ C
Ph	0		546	546	544	544	542	540
	10		507	507	507	502	500	497
	30		492	492	492	490	490	490
	50		490	490	490	490	490	488
	70		490	490	490	490	488	488
	90		490	490	490	488	488	488
pFPh	0		546	546	544	544	542	540
	10		511	511	509	507	505	505
	30		511	511	505	505	503	493
	50		507	507	505	500	498	495
	70		511	511	505	503	497	495
	90		7	7	7	7	7	7

matrix is largely enhanced as the temperature is increased, allowing the formation of the *cis* and *trans* isomers (Fig. 1).

The absorption maximum also shows a progressive shift to higher energies as the Ph/Si ratio in the matrix is increased, at a given temperature. Increasing the amount of the organic functional substituents in the structure results in a decrease of the polarity of the matrix leading to a shift of the position of the absorption band of the photochromic dye to the UV.^{14,17} This behaviour, in pFPh functionalized samples, is observed to a much smaller extent, due to the higher polarity of these substituents.

Bleaching kinetics

Upon cessation of UV irradiation, the photochromic molecules in the film undergo thermal bleaching in the dark, recovering their original colourless form. The kinetics of the bleaching process is strongly dependent on both the composition of the embedding matrix and the temperature of the sample. The kinetics of the bleaching process in all samples follow a bi-exponential decay: the kinetic constants increase as the amount of Ph or pFPh substituents in the matrix and temperature is increased.

The photochromic molecules embedded in matrices modified with pFPh substituents show a faster bleaching than in the corresponding Ph functionalized matrices. This can be attributed to the smaller pore size, resulting in a larger steric hindrance of the opening mechanism of the photochromic molecule, leading to faster bleaching kinetics. Fig. 9 shows the bleaching kinetics of samples prepared with Ph and pFPh substituents and measured at different temperatures, represented as absorbance vs. time.

Raising the temperature of the samples, from 10 to 60 μ C, resulted in faster bleaching kinetics in both Ph and pFPh functionalized samples. The first kinetic constant (k_1), assigned to photochromic molecules in pores rich in organic functional substituents,¹⁴ was strongly increased as the temperature of the sample was raised, while the second constant (k_2), assigned to dye molecules in pores rich in OH groups, showed no dependence on the temperature. This behaviour is shown in Fig. 10 for samples having a R/Si ratio of 0.7 (R70).

Fig. 9 Thermal bleaching kinetics of the photochromic effect in Ph and pPPh functionalized samples at different temperatures.

Fig. 10 Kinetic constants of the photochromic naphthopyran molecules in functionalized ormosil matrices at different temperatures.

Conclusions

Photochromic naphthopyran molecules were embedded in sol-gel prepared Ph and pPPh functionalized silica films. The photochromic properties of the naphthopyran molecules embedded in the different ormosil matrices were measured as a function of temperature. The temperature plays an important role in the colour intensity of the irradiated samples, as it has a direct effect on the bleaching kinetic constants and the equilibrium between the coloured and colourless forms of the dye. The bleaching process of the photochromic molecules embedded in these ormosil matrices was strongly accelerated by temperature in all samples. However, this effect was observed mainly on one of the kinetic constants: that assigned to the pores rich in organic substituents (k_1).¹⁴ The position of the absorption maximum was also found to depend on the temperature, showing a blue shift as the temperature is increased. This is due to the reduced mobility of the molecules, particularly in pPPh functionalized matrices, which limits the formation of the *trans*-isomer of the open coloured merocyanine at low temperatures. The more polar character

of the pPPh substituents as compared with the Ph substituents leads to much stronger interactions between the pPPh substituents and the OH groups on the surface of the pores (hydrogen bonds). As a result of these interactions, much thinner films are formed due to a drastic reduction of the size of the pores, leading therefore to an increase of the steric hindrance affecting the mechanism of formation of the coloured forms. The increased steric hindrance in more polar matrices leads to faster bleaching kinetics and hence to a lower colour intensity of the films during irradiation with UV light.

The ability to control the interaction between the photochromic molecules and the embedding ormosil matrix by the organic functional substituents in the matrix and the temperature opens a new way for the design of materials with defined photochromic properties.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by a research project from Comunidad de Madrid (GR/MAT/0445/2004), and from

MEC (NAN2004-09317-C04-02 and MAT2005-05131-C02-01). The authors are grateful to Dr Luis Vazquez Burgos from the ICM-CONICOR for the AFM micrographs and to PPG Industries Inc. for the generous donation of the photochromic molecule used in this work. Rosario Pardo is grateful to MEC for a doctoral studentship.

References

- 1 B. Van Gemert, in *Organic Photochromic and Thermochromic Compounds*, ed. J.C. Crano and R. Guglielmetti, Plenum Press, New York, 1999, vol. 1, ch. 3.
 - 2 B. Luccioni-Houze', M. Campredon, R. Guglielmetti and G. Giusti, *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 1997, 297, 161.
 - 3 D. B. Knowles, *US Pat.*, 1993, 5238981; D. B. Knowles, *US Pat.*, 1994, 5369158.
 - 4 A. Kumar, B. Van Gemert and D. B. Knowles, *US Pat.*, 1995, 5458814.
 - 5 B. Van Gemert and A. Kumar, *US Pat.*, 1997, 5637262.
 - 6 C. M. Nelson, A. Chopra, D. B. Knowles, B. Van Gemert and A. Kumar, *US Pat.*, 2002, 6348604.
 - 7 A. Kumar, *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 1997, 297, 139.
 - 8 L. Merlini, *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1975, 18, 159.
 - 9 M. Zayat and D. Levy, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2003, 13, 727.
 - 10 C. J. Brinker and G. W. Sherer, *Sol-Gel Science: The Physics and Chemistry of Sol-Gel Processing*, Academic Press, San Diego, 1990.
 - 11 D. Avnir, D. Levy and R. Reisfel, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, 88, 5956.
 - 12 D. Levy and D. Avnir, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1988, 92, 4734.
 - 13 D. Levy and L. Esquivias, *Adv. Mater.*, 1995, 7, 120.
 - 14 M. Zayat, R. Pardo and D. Levy, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2003, 13, 2899.
 - 15 R. Pardo, M. Zayat and D. Levy, *J. Mater. Chem.*, 2005, 15, 703.
 - 16 C. Reichardt, *Chem. Rev.*, 1994, 94, 2319.
 - 17 C. Rottman, G. Grader and D. Avnir, *Chem. Mater.*, 2001, 13, 3631.
 - 18 C. Rottman, G. S. Grader, Y. De Hazan and D. Avnir, *Langmuir*, 1996, 12, 5505.
 - 19 D. K. Lee and Y. S. Kang, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2003, 107, 1543.
 - 20 S. Delbaere, B. Luccioni-Houze', C. Bochu, Y. Teral, M. Campredon and G. Vermeersch, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1998, 5, 1153.
 - 21 J. Hobley, V. Malatesta, R. Millini, W. Giroladini, L. Wis, M. Goto, M. Kishimoto and H. Fukumura, *Chem. Commun.*, 2000, 1339.
-